

On a problem concerning the Smarandache friendly prime pairs

Felice Russo

Via A. Infante 7

67051 Avezzano (Aq) Italy

felice.russo@katamail.com

Abstract

In this paper a question posed in [1] and concerning the Smarandache friendly prime pairs is analysed.

Introduction

In [1] the Smarandache friendly prime pairs are defined as those prime pairs (p,q) such that:

$$\sum_{x=p}^q x = p \cdot q \quad (1)$$

where x denote the primes between p and q . In other words the Smarandache friendly prime pairs are the pairs (p,q) such that the sum of the primes between p and q is equal to the product of p and q .

As example let's consider the pair $(2,5)$. In this case $2+3+5=2 \cdot 5$ and then 2 and 5 are friendly primes. The other three pairs given in the mentioned paper are: $(3,13)$, $(5,31)$ and $(7,53)$. Then the following open questions have been posed:

Are there infinitely many friendly prime pairs?

Is there for every prime p a prime q such that (p,q) is a Smarandache friendly prime pair?

In this paper we analyse the last question and a shortcut to explore the first conjecture is reported.

Results

First of all let's analyse the case $p=11$. Let's indicate:

$$f(11,q) = \sum_{x=11}^q x \quad \text{and} \quad g(11,q) = 11 \cdot q$$

where x denotes always the primes between 11 and q .

A computer program with Ubasic software package has been written to calculate the difference between $g(11,q)$ and $f(11,q)$ for the 164 primes q subsequent to 11. Here below the trend of that difference.

As we can see the difference starts to increase, arrives to a maximum and then starts to decrease and once pass the x axis decrease in average linearly. The same thing is true for all the other primes p.

So for every prime p the search of its friend q can be performed up to:

$$g(p, q) - f(p, q) \leq -M$$

where M is a positive constant.

For the first 1000 primes M has been chosen equal to 10^5 .

No further friendly prime pair besides those reported in [1] has been found. According to those experimental results we are enough confident to pose the following conjecture:

Not all the primes have a friend, that is there are prime p such that there isn't a prime q such that the (1) is true.

Moreover a further check of friendly prime pairs for all primes larger than 1000 and smaller than 10000 has been performed choosing $M=1000000$.

No further friendly prime pair has been found. Those results seem to point out that the number of friendly prime pairs is finite.

Question:

Are (2,5), (3,13), (5,31) and (7,53) the only Smarandache friendly prime pairs?

References.

[1] A. Murthy, *Smarandache friendly numbers and a few more sequences*, Smarandache Notions Journal, Vol. 12 N. 1-2-3 Spring 2001